

Research review paper

Understanding glycosylation: Regulation through the metabolic flux of precursor pathways

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ABSTRACT

Glycosylation is how proteins and lipids are modified with complex carbohydrates known as glycans. The post-translational modification of proteins with glycans is not a template-driven process in the same way as genetic transcription or protein translation. Glycosylation is instead dynamically regulated by metabolic flux. This metabolic flux is determined by the concentrations and activities of the glycotransferase enzymes, which synthesise glycans, the metabolites that act as their precursors and transporter proteins. This review provides an overview of the metabolic pathways underlying glycan synthesis. Pathological dysregulation of glycosylation, particularly increased glycosylation occurring during inflammation, is also elucidated. The resulting inflammatory hyperglycosylation acts as a glycosignature of disease, and we report on the changes in the metabolic pathways which feed into glycan synthesis, revealing alterations to key enzymes. Finally, we examine studies in developing metabolic inhibitors targeting these critical enzymes. These results provide the tools for researchers investigating the role of glycan metabolism in inflammation and have helped to identify promising glycotherapeutic approaches to inflammation.

1. Introduction

Glycosylation is the decoration of biomolecules with carbohydrates

known as glycans (Schjoldager et al., 2020), (Li et al., 2022). Protein glycosylation is a post-translational modification vital to protein function and folding, as a glycan's attachment alters the polypeptide's

Abbreviation: 2-DG, 2-deoxyglucose; 2FF, 2-deoxy-2-fluoro-L-Fucose; 2F-PAF, 2F-Peracetyl fucose; 3PO, 3-(3-pyridinyl)-1-(4-pyridinyl)-2-propen-1-one; 5 T-Fuc, 5-thiofucose; 6-Alk-Fuc, 6-Alkynyl-fucose; AAL, *Aleuria aurantia*; AD, Alzheimer's disease; CHO, Chinese hamster ovary; CMAS, N-acetylneuraminidase cytidyltransferase; CMP, Cytidine monophosphate; COAM, Chlorite-oxidised oxyamylose; Dol-P, Dolichol-phosphate; DON, 6-diazo-5-oxo-L-norleucine; DPAGT1, N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase 1; *E. coli*, *Escherichia coli*; ECM, Extracellular matrix; EMT, Epithelial-mesenchymal transition; ER, Endoplasmic reticulum; FCSK, Fucose kinase; FPGT, Fucose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase; FRET, Fluorescence resonance energy transfer; Fru-6-P, Fructose-6-phosphate; Fuc, Fucose; FuCA1, Lysosomal fucosidase; FUT, Fucosyltransferase; FX, GDP-fucose-synthase; G6PD, Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase; Gal, Galactose; GalNAc, N-acetylgalactosamine; GBM, Glioblastoma; GDP, Guanosine diphosphate; GDP-Fuc, Guanosine diphosphate-fucose; GFAT1, Glutamine:fructose-6-phosphate aminotransferase 1; GPI, glucose-6-phosphate isomerase; Glc, Glucose; Glc-6-P, Glucosamine-6-phosphate; GlcNAc, N-acetylglucosamine; GLUT, Glucose transporter; GMD, GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase; GNE, UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2 epimerase; GNK, GlcNAc kinase; Golgi, Golgi apparatus; HBP, Hexosamine biosynthetic pathway; hiMG, Human induced pluripotent stem cells derived microglia; HK, Hexokinase; IVD, Intervertebral disc; KO, Knockout; MAA, *Maackia Amurensis*; Man, Mannose; ManNAc, N-acetylmannosamine; MGAT, N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase; MNK, N-acetylmannosamine kinase; MPI, Mannose-6 phosphate isomerase; NANP, N-acetylneuraminidase phosphatase; NANS, N-acetylneuraminidase synthase; Neu5Ac, Sialic acid; NMR, Nuclear magnetic resonance; NP, Nucleus Pulposus; NST, Nucleotide sugar transporter; OGA, O-GlcNAcase; OGT, O-GlcNAc transferase; OST, Oligosaccharyltransferase; PD, Parkinson's disease; PDAC, Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma; PGM3, Phosphoglucomutase 3; PHA, *Phaseolus vulgaris*; PSL, *Polyporus squamosus*; RA, Rheumatoid arthritis; RASF, Rheumatoid arthritis-synovial fibroblasts; SLC35, Solute carrier family 35; SNA, *Sambucus nigra*; SSA, *Sambucus sieboldiana*; ST, Sialyltransferase; TCR, T cell receptor; TNBC, Triple-negative breast cancer; UAP, Acetylhexosamine pyrophosphorylase; UC, Ulcerative colitis; UDP-GlcNAc, Uridine diphosphate N-acetylglucosamine; UEA-I, *Ulex europaeus* agglutinin I; UTP, Uridine triphosphate; WGA, *Wheat germ agglutinin*.

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biophysical properties (Aebi, 2013). Furthermore, glycosylation plays a role in endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, as the accumulation of misfolded proteins in the ER activates the unfolded protein response (Hetzel and Papa, 2018). The synthesis of glycans is a highly complex process involving more than 200 enzymes, a range of sugar phosphate intermediates and nucleotide sugars (Schjoldager et al., 2020). Glycan synthesis occurs in the ER and the Golgi apparatus (Golgi). ER-resident glycosyltransferase enzymes regulate glycan elongation, while glycosidases control glycan trimming and remodelling (Csala et al., 2012). Metabolic flux is the rate at which metabolites are processed through pathways involving a series of intermediates (Stephanopoulos, 1999), (Long and Antoniewicz, 2019). Sufficient metabolic flux through the glycan precursor pathways is essential to sustaining glycan synthesis. Glycosylation is not a template-driven process in the same way as gene transcription or protein translation. As glycosylation occurs in the ER and the Golgi, the availability of nucleotide sugar precursors, glycosyltransferase enzyme levels, and activity within the compartments of these organelles regulate the metabolic flux of glycosylation (McDonald et al., 2016), (Reily et al., 2019). This multi-level regulation makes glycosylation a complex process. Analysis of the metabolic pathways synthesising glycans is critical to understanding glycosylation and identifying novel and glyco-focused biomarkers and therapies.

Glycans are recognised by glycan-binding proteins, such as the selectins to induce inflammation (Smith and Bertozzi, 2021). Adding to the complexity are changes in the environment of cells, which can induce rapid and dramatic alterations in the glycans produced. This results in potential pathological conditions due to the many players that play a role in the dynamic processes of glycan synthesis and maintenance (Rebello et al., 2022a). Inflammation is a potent inducer of glycosylation changes as glycans significantly regulate immune cells across various tissue types. For example, the glycans found in the brain or intervertebral disc (IVD) have been examined. In these tissues, inflammation induces alterations in glycan expression profiles, with specific glycan structures increasing in abundance and others decreasing (Joyce et al., 2021), (Rebello et al., 2021). Therefore, understanding the changes observed in glycosylation provides an exciting opportunity to increase our understanding of disease progression. Furthermore, understanding the role of glycosylation changes in disease could lead to opportunities for potential glycotherapeutic strategies. This review focuses on the glycosylation changes in human disease from a metabolic perspective. It aims to provide the reader with an understanding of the metabolic pathways underlying glycan synthesis, *N*-glycosylation changes observed in inflammation and disease, and modulation of glycosylation by metabolic means.

2. Glycans: posttranslational modifications

Glycans are mono-, poly- or oligosaccharide chains that can be attached to proteins (forming glycoproteins) and lipids (forming glycolipids). They are the most complicated posttranslational modification, where a sugar molecule is bound to an amino acid. Glycans consist of monosaccharide building blocks connected through various chemical linkage types. Glycans can be subdivided into groups based on these sugar-amino acid bonds (Spiro, 2002). The following sections will discuss the diversity of possible structures into which glycans are found and the pathways that synthesise these monosaccharides.

2.1. Structural diversity of glycans

Protein glycosylation can be divided into *N*-linked glycosylation, *O*-linked glycosylation, and *O*-GlcNAcylation. The glycan is attached solely to an asparagine residue in the protein backbone in *N*-linked glycosylation. In contrast, in *O*-linked glycosylation, the glycan can be attached to either a serine or threonine residue. *N*-linked glycans always contain a pentasaccharide core consisting of two *N*-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) residues and three mannose (Man) residues (Higel et al., 2016). *N*-

glycans can be divided into three groups; oligomannose, in which only Man residues extend from the core; complex *N*-glycans, in which antennae extend from the core initiated by a GlcNAc residue; and hybrid *N*-glycans, in which a combination of Man and GlcNAc extended antennae extend from the core (Varki et al., 2022). An overview is presented in Fig. 1. *O*-linked glycans are usually linked through *N*-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc), Fucose (Fuc), or Man residues (Krusius et al., 1986), (Carraway and Hull, 1989), (Haltiwanger and Stanley, 2002). In *O*-glycosylation, glycans are attached through the hydroxyl side groups on either a serine or threonine residue of the protein (Reily et al., 2019). GalNAc-linked *O*-glycans, also called mucin-type *O*-glycans, are abundant on many extracellular and secreted glycoproteins (Bennett et al., 2012). Mucins, which form a barrier between endothelial cells and mucosal surfaces of the body, are decorated with *O*-glycosylation sites where *O*-glycans form a gel-like barrier to protect cell surfaces and glycoproteins from environmental stress, microbial function, and self-recognition by the immune system (Reily et al., 2019).

O-GlcNAcylation is a more dynamic modification than other glycan types, as it can be reversibly removed by *O*-GlcNAcase (OGA) (Chang et al., 2020). In *O*-GlcNAcylation, a single GlcNAc monosaccharide is attached to a serine or threonine residues of target proteins through a β -linkage by the *O*-GlcNAc transferase enzyme (OGT) (Holt and Hart, 1986), (Haltiwanger et al., 1990). Conversely, GlcNAc can be removed from proteins through activity of the *O*-GlcNAcase (OGA) enzyme, making this a more transient modification than other glycans (Dong and Hart, 1994). *O*-GlcNAcylation changes target protein function by regulating the cellular location, protein stability, and protein-protein interaction. Furthermore, *O*-GlcNAcylation has been shown to have intricate crosstalk with phosphorylation as it competes for modification at serine or threonine residues (Wells et al., 2001), (Chang et al., 2020).

Although *O*-glycosylation and *O*-GlcNAcylation are relevant topics, they will not be further discussed in this review. Instead, *N*-glycosylation, the most abundant glycosylation type, is the focus of this review.

2.2. Synthesis of *N*-glycans

N-glycan synthesis occurs in the ER and the Golgi apparatus (Varki et al., 2022). Monosaccharides must first be bound by a nucleotide sugar, which results in an activated form (Fig. 1). The activation of sialic acid (Neu5Ac) with cytidine monophosphate (CMP) occurs in the nucleus, while all other glycans are activated in the cytosol (Kean et al., 2004) (Nji et al., 2019). The activated nucleotide sugars are transported into the ER and Golgi apparatus by nucleotide sugar transporter (NST) proteins, where they react with the glycosyltransferase enzymes, such as sialyltransferases (STs) or fucosyltransferases (FUTs) to produce a diverse range of glycan structures (Bosmann et al., 1968), (Kim et al., 1971) (van Scherpenzeel et al., 2022). *N*-Glycan synthesis utilises the lipid carrier dolichol-phosphate (Dol-P) as an oligosaccharide donor (Roth et al., 2010). The initial step in this pathway involves the enzyme dolichyl-phosphate *N*-acetylglucosaminophosphotransferase 1 (DPAGT1) transferring GlcNAc from uridine diphosphate *N*-acetylglucosamine (UDP-GlcNAc) to Dol-P. DPAGT1 is integrated into the membrane of the cytosolic face of the ER, with a structure composed of ten transmembrane helices (Yoo et al., 2018). Subsequent addition of a second GlcNAc and three Man residues by glycosyltransferases happen on the cytosolic side of the ER. Then, Dol-P flips to the ER lumen, where seven hexose sugars are added to the precursor sugar. On the inside of the lumen, four Man and three glucose (Glc) residues are added to the Man₅GlcNAc₂ *N*-glycan, transferred from the membrane-embedded Dol-P-mannose and Dol-P-Glucose donor substrates (Bloch et al., 2020). The resulting *N*-glycan Glc₃Man₉GlcNAc₂ structure is then transferred *en bloc* to the target asparagine residue of a protein by the oligosaccharyltransferase (OST) complex (Chavan and Lennarz, 2006) (Braunger et al., 2018). OST is close to the ER protein translocation channel and can access nascent polypeptides. OST scans the polypeptide for asparagine acceptor sites as it emerges from the channel and then transfers the

Fig. 1. Top panel: main mammalian types of glycosylation. *N*-Glycans are attached to the protein at the asparagine residue and can be divided into three groups; high mannose *N*-glycans consisting of only mannose residues extending from the core, complex *N*-glycans where decorated branches extend from the core, and hybrid *N*-glycans in which a combination of mannose and decorated branches are observed. In *O*-glycans, an *N*-acetylgalactosamine attaches to a serine or threonine residue decorated by various attachments forming *O*-glycan cores. *O*-GlcNAcylation, in which a single *N*-acetylglucosamine is attached by OGT to a serine or threonine residue or removed by OGA, acts as a switch for many proteins and enzymes. The *N*-Glycan synthesis starts on the endoplasmic reticulum membrane, attached to dolichol-P, forming a $\text{Glc}_3\text{Man}_9\text{GlcNAc}_2$ *N*-glycan before flipping to the inside of the ER lumen where it is then transferred *en bloc* to an asparagine residue of newly synthesised proteins. Here, the three glucose are trimmed off, and the protein moves towards the Golgi apparatus (Golgi). In the *cis*-Golgi, further trimming of mannose residues by α -Mannosidases takes place to form a $\text{Man}_3\text{GlcNAc}_2$ core before moving to the medial Golgi where attachment of GlcNAc and fucose residues takes place by various MGAT, and FUTs. The *trans*-Golgi decoration with Galactose and Sialic acids completes the synthesis. Bottom panel: an overview of the activated monosaccharide residues attached to their nucleotide carriers. Mannose and fucose monosaccharides are carried by guanosine diphosphate, glucose, galactose, *N*-acetylglucosamine, and *N*-acetylgalactosamine monosaccharides are carried by uridine diphosphate, and the cytidine monophosphate nucleotide carriers carry sialic acid. Abbreviations: OGT: *O*-GlcNAc transferase, OGA: *O*-GlcNAcase, ER: endoplasmic reticulum, OST: oligosaccharyltransferase, MGAT: *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase, FUT: fucosyltransferase, ST: sialyltransferase, GalT: galactosyltransferase, GDP: guanosine diphosphate, UDP: uridine diphosphate, CMP: cytidine monophosphate.

oligosaccharide structure (Shrimal et al., 2015). Following the transfer of the oligosaccharide onto the protein, containing nine Man residues, this structure is trimmed by glucosidases α -glucosidase I and II, removing three terminal glucose residues (Kalz-Füller et al., 1995). Before leaving the ER and transferring to the Golgi, α -mannosidase I (MAN1B1) removes the terminal mannose residue from the central arm of the structure, resulting in $\text{Man}_8\text{GlcNAc}_2$. In the *cis*-Golgi region, further trimming of mannose residues by Golgi class I α 1-2 mannosidases IA, IB, and IC takes place, resulting in a $\text{Man}_5\text{GlcNAc}_2$ structure, which is then moved to the *medial*-Golgi (Herscovics et al., 1994), (Legler et al., 2018). Here, complex and hybrid *N*-glycans are synthesised following the addition of a GlcNAc residue by *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase GlcNAc-TI (MGAT 1) to the trimmed mannose structures, resulting in the formation of $\text{GlcNAcMan}_5\text{GlcNAc}_2$, with

several enzymes competing for this structure as a substrate (Ednie et al., 2019). The Golgi α -mannosidase II (MAN2A1 & MAN2A2) enzyme, which trims terminal mannose residues, is one of these enzymes, and this trimming reaction results in the production of $\text{GlcNAcMan}_3\text{GlcNAc}_2$ (Kadirvelraj et al., 2018). Additional GlcNAc residues are added by MGAT enzymes, such as MGAT4 or MGAT5. The action of these MGATs at potential branch points can result in complex, asymmetric bi-, tri- and tetra-antennary *N*-glycans (Liu et al., 2018).

Further modification of these immature *N*-glycans includes the addition of monosaccharide residues to the inner-core GlcNAc, elongating the GlcNAc branches by adding additional sugar residues, and the capping of elongated branches (García-García et al., 2021). Core modification of GlcNAc includes the addition of a fucose residue by the α 1-6 fucosyltransferase 8 (FUT8) enzyme. The structural features of the

N-glycans determine the kinetics of the reactions catalysed by this enzyme. FUT8 prefers specific structures, such as biantennary glycans (García-García et al., 2021). Further elongation of *N*-glycans starts with the addition of galactose (Gal) residues to the GlcNAc residues, which can then be end-capped by the addition of Neu5Ac residues, Fuc, Gal, and GlcNAc (Varki et al., 2022). Therefore, the diversity of *N*-glycan structures is substantial and depends on the relative activity of a wide array of glycosyltransferase enzymes. The metabolic flux between these glycotransferases and their substrates is a dynamic complex system regulated by a variety of factors, such as rates of the multi-step synthesis of activated nucleotide sugars, their transport into the Golgi apparatus by NSTs, the relative expression and activity levels of glycosyltransferase enzymes, and their localisation within the Golgi (McDonald et al., 2016) as will be discussed throughout this review.

Glycans synthesis relies on the availability of free monosaccharide

substrate to facilitate the enzymatic reactions that link monosaccharides together to form *N*-glycans. In the next section, we highlight some key pathways underlying glycan synthesis to form various monosaccharide substrates fuelling *N*-glycan synthesis.

3. Synthesis of glycans

Glycans are comprised of a variety of hexoses derived from glucose and pentoses derived from fructose. In *N*-glycosylation, the bond formed between the glycan and the asparagine amino acid is facilitated by the GlcNAc monosaccharide. The *N*-glycan core consists of two GlcNAc residues, and GlcNAc is also used as an anchor from which the antennae observed in complex and hybrid *N*-glycans extend. This makes GlcNAc a vital monosaccharide for synthesising various glycan types, as will be discussed in the following sections, along with the metabolic pathways

Fig. 2. Two major glucose-utilising pathways; the glycolysis and hexosamine biosynthetic pathways. Both pathways share the first two steps converting glucose that enters the cell to glucose-6-phosphate by hexokinase and subsequent conversion to fructose-6-phosphate by glucose-6-phosphate isomerase. Glutamine:fructose-6-phosphate transaminase (GFAT) catalyses the rate-limiting step of the HBP, converting fructose-6-phosphate and glutamine into glucosamine-6-phosphate and glutamate and, as such, is a key regulating enzyme of the HBP. Glucosamine-6-phosphate *N*-acetyltransferase (GNA1) converts glucosamine-6-phosphate into *N*-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate, requiring the input of acetylated coenzyme-A, which relies on fatty acid metabolism. Phosphoglucomutase (PGM3) then converts *N*-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate into *N*-acetylglucosamine-1-phosphate before finally, UDP-*N*-acetylhexosamine pyrophosphorylase (UAP) converts *N*-acetylglucosamine-1-phosphate and uridine triphosphate it into UDP-GlcNAc. UDP-GlcNAc is a vital substrate for glycan synthesis as part of the *N*-glycan core, as well as the anchor point for extended branching of complex and hybrid *N*-glycans. Abbreviations: HK: hexokinase, GPI: glucose-6-phosphate isomerase, PFK1: phosphofruktokinase, ALDO: aldolase, TPI: triosephosphate isomerase, GAPDH: glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, PGK: phosphoglycerate kinase, PGM: phosphoglycerate mutase, ENO: enolase, PK: pyruvate kinase, GFAT: glutamine:fructose-6-phosphate transaminase, GNA1: glucosamine-6-*N*-acetyltransferase, PGM3: phosphoglucomutase, UPA: UDP-*N*-acetylhexosamine pyrophosphorylase, UDP-GlcNAc: uridine diphosphate *N*-acetylglucosamine.

which synthesise several other key glycans.

3.1. *N*-acetylglucosamine synthesis

UDP-GlcNAc is synthesised by the hexosamine biosynthetic pathway (HBP) in cells and requires input from major macromolecules, including glucose, glutamine, acetylated-coenzyme-A, UTP and acetate, thereby being at the crossroads of nutrient usage (Akella et al., 2019). This makes the HBP a nutrient-sensing metabolic pathway. The HBP metabolises about 2-5% of the glucose that enters the cell to form UDP-GlcNAc (Marshall et al., 1991). The HBP contributes to glycan biosynthesis by converting glucose to UDP-GlcNAc through a six-step pathway which shares the first two steps with glycolysis (Fig. 2). Briefly, glucose is phosphorylated by hexokinase (HK), resulting in glucose-6-phosphate. Then, glucose-6-phosphate isomerase (GPI) converts glucose-6-phosphate into fructose-6-phosphate (Vanhove et al., 2019). Next, glutamine:fructose-6-phosphate aminotransferase 1 (GFAT1) catalyses the rate-limiting step in the HBP, converting fructose-6-phosphate (Fru-6-P) and glutamine into glucosamine-6-phosphate and glutamate (Walter et al., 2020). Glucosamine-6-phosphate is then converted into *N*-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate by glucosamine-6-phosphate *N*-acetyltransferase (GNA1) which requires acetylated-coenzyme-A, a product of fatty acid metabolism. Next, phosphoglucomutase 3 (PGM3) isomerises *N*-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate into *N*-acetylglucosamine-1-phosphate, and finally, UDP-*N*-acetylhexosamine pyrophosphorylase (UAP) converts *N*-acetylglucosamine-1 and uridine triphosphate (UTP) into UDP-GlcNAc and diphosphate. The glucosamine that enters the cell can also enter the HBP through GNK (GlcNAc kinase) phosphorylation, bypassing reliance on GFAT and glutamine availability (Akella et al., 2019). GFAT1 is a modular enzyme, with a glutaminase domain controlling the hydrolysis of glutamine and a transferase domain which catalyses the isomerisation of Fru-6-phosphate to glucosamine-6-phosphate. Given its role in synthesising UDP-GlcNAc, metabolic flux through the HBP significantly regulates glycosylation. However, it is not the only source of UDP-GlcNAc for cells (Ruegenberg et al., 2021). UDP-GlcNAc can also be salvaged through a lysosomal salvage pathway through the enzyme GlcNAc Kinase, which phosphorylates GlcNAc to GlcNAc-6-phosphate from lysosomal degraded glycoconjugates, bypassing GFAT dependency (Weihofen et al., 2006). Intracellular glutamine availability is required for the synthesis of UDP-GlcNAc by the HBP. Furthermore, intracellular glutamine levels increase the UDP-GlcNAc levels, as demonstrated by the finding that in human cervical cancer cells and murine embryonic fibroblasts, a progressive increase in the concentration of glutamine, from 0 mM to 8 mM causes a parallel increase in UDP-GlcNAc (2.5 fold increase) or protein *O*-GlcNAcylation (2 fold) respectively (Hamiel et al., 2009), (Abdel Rahman et al., 2013), (Chiaradonna et al., 2018). The availability of glutamine is, therefore, critical for the intracellular production of UDP-GlcNAc and downstream *N*-glycosylation. UDP-GlcNAc is one of the essential metabolites fuelling glycosylation and is a crucial regulatory factor, as will be discussed throughout this review.

UDP-GlcNAc is the substrate for the Golgi Beta-1,6-*N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase (MGAT) family of enzymes; MGAT1, 2, 4 & 5. These enzymes regulate the branching of *N*-glycans, with the extent of branching in glycans depending upon the metabolic flux of MGAT enzymes (Mkhikian et al., 2016). The relative activity of each enzyme and the concentration of UDP-GlcNAc determines this flux. The MGATs have different affinities for their shared substrate, with MGAT1 having the highest affinity, ~250-fold higher than MGAT5 (Mkhikian et al., 2011). As the MGATs compete for UDP-GlcNAc substrate, when its concentration is low, and MGAT1 expression is high, MGAT1 outcompetes the other branching enzymes. This reduces the supply of UDP-GlcNAc to MGAT4 & MGAT5, resulting in reduced branching. However, when the concentration of UDP-GlcNAc increases sufficiently, MGAT4 & MGAT5 can act upon the increased pool of their substrate, leading to increased *N*-glycan branching (Mkhikian et al., 2011). Along the membranes of the

Golgi apparatus, MGAT enzymes can self-assemble into complexes with NST proteins (Khoder-Agha et al., 2019). Ternary complexes formed between the MGATs and the NSTs were revealed in fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) assays. MGAT1, MGAT2, MGAT3, and MGAT4B were all found to interact with other MGATs, while MGAT5 did not interact with any other MGATs. The MAN2A2 enzyme appeared to act as the central hub in these MGAT interactions. Members of the NST family, the UDP-Gal transporter SLC35A2, UDP-GlcNAc transporter SLC35A3 and an orphan transporter SLC35A4, encoded by the solute carrier family 35 (SLC35) group of genes were also analysed in the FRET experiments. Heteromeric complexes were formed between these NSTs, as with the MGATs. As well as these complexes, the MGATs also interacted with NSTs. These experiments demonstrate that multi-enzyme/multi-transporter complexes assemble in the membranes of the Golgi (Khoder-Agha et al., 2019). This work provides researchers with an updated model for the spatial arrangement of *N*-glycan synthesis, which will help provide insights into how best to analyse the glycan branching process. The complexes that the MGATs can form in the Golgi, along with the metabolic flux between these enzymes and activated sugar metabolites, comprise highly dynamic systems demonstrating the complexity of glycosylation.

UDP-GlcNAc is not only a substrate for glycan synthesis but also used to form other monosaccharides that ultimately end up in glycans. One monosaccharide derived from UDP-GlcNAc is Neu5Ac, which is prevalent in many *N*-glycans.

3.2. *Sialic acid* synthesis

The synthesis of the nine-carbon Neu5Ac monosaccharide is another critical metabolic pathway in glycosylation (Gottschalk, 1951). Neu5Ac synthesis begins with the HBP-derived UDP-GlcNAc as a precursor. This pathway converts UDP-GlcNAc into CMP-Neu5Ac, the activated nucleotide sugar which 20 different STs can then use to produce sialylated glycans with either α 2-3, α 2-6 or α 2-8 linkages (Keppler et al., 1999). Sialic acid metabolism involves several enzymes, with two enzymes: UDP-*N*-acetylglucosamine 2-epimerase (GNE), also known as *N*-acetylmannosamine kinase (MNK), and *N*-acetylneuraminic acid cytidylyltransferase (CMAS) being particularly important (Fig. 4). Various studies have been conducted in recent years elucidating the mechanisms of these key metabolic enzymes, contributing to the development of targeted inhibition of glycan metabolism. GNE controls the rate-limiting steps in Neu5Ac synthesis, catalysing the conversion of UDP-GlcNAc into *N*-acetylmannosamine (ManNAc) with its epimerase domain and the phosphorylation of ManNAc into ManNAc-6-P with its kinase domain. GNE can bind to UDP-GlcNAc, its substrate, and CMP-Neu5Ac, which causes feedback inhibition by binding to an allosteric site (Chen et al., 2016). Following the GNE conversion steps, the *N*-acetylneuraminic acid synthase (NANS) enzyme converts ManNAc-6-P into Neu5Ac-9-P, and then the *N*-acetylneuraminic acid phosphatase (NANP) dephosphorylates Neu5Ac-9-P, producing free Neu5Ac. Knockout experiments in Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells demonstrated that sialylation was not significantly disrupted in NANP knockout (KO) cells, compared with GNE, NANS and CMAS KO cells, where sialylation was inhibited (Willems et al., 2019). Following the action of these NANS and NANP enzymes comes the essential activity of CMAS, which activates free Neu5Ac with CMP before this nucleotide sugar is transferred to the Golgi, where it can be used by the different STs to produce sialylated glycans. An analysis of metabolites collected from solid tumours demonstrated that increased expression and activity of CMAS causes dysregulation of flux through the sialic acid metabolic pathway and that the levels of the CMP-Neu5Ac metabolite are increased in cancer. However, the precise mechanisms by which CMAS regulates sialic acid metabolism still require further studies (Teoh et al., 2018).

The studies described here have shown that GNE and CMAS are critical regulators of sialic acid metabolism. As we will discuss further, the activity of these key metabolic enzymes becomes dysregulated

during pathology and act as glycosignatures of inflammation. Therefore, these enzymes are valid targets for designing novel glycotherapies such as metabolic inhibitors.

3.3. Mannose synthesis

Another key monosaccharide in *N*-glycan synthesis is Man. In the *N*-glycan core, 9 Man residues are required to form a single *N*-glycan. Furthermore, *N*-glycan maturation relies on the specific trimming of Man residues. Man can be generated from glucose or mannose, with mannose-6-phosphate as a key precursor metabolite. Roughly 10–45% of the mannose found in *N*-glycans derives from exogenous mannose, which is phosphorylated by HK. This phosphorylated mannose is a key intermediate in synthesising glycans and can be converted into glycan structures (Xu et al., 2019). The major source for the synthesis of mannose is glucose-derived (Ichikawa et al., 2014). Fru-6-P is formed as an intermediate of the glycolysis pathway, which is converted by the mannose-6 phosphate isomerase (MPI) enzyme. Mannose-6-phosphate is subsequently converted to mannose-1-phosphate by phosphomannomutase. Finally, mannose-1-phosphate is coupled to the guanosine diphosphate (GDP) nucleoside to form the activated GDP-Man. GDP-

Man can then be used by mannosyltransferase enzymes or converted to Dol-P (Ichikawa et al., 2014). Additionally, GDP-Man can be used as a substrate for synthesising fucose, another prevalent monosaccharide in *N*-glycans, involving further metabolic steps which will be discussed.

3.4. Fucose synthesis

Fucose can be derived from different sources, the *de novo*, the salvage pathway, or exogenous fucose (Coffey et al., 1964). The majority of guanosine diphosphate-fucose (GDP-Fuc) is derived from the *de novo* pathway, providing 90–95% of this nucleotide sugar (Skurska et al., 2022). In *de novo* fucose synthesis, mannose or glucose are used as precursors, with GDP-Man being converted to GDP-Fuc through various intermediary species. The fucose salvage pathway, has two branches. In the first, extracellular fucose is transported into the cytosol, then converted to GDP-fucose (Fig. 3). Alternatively, the lysosomal α -L-fucosidase (FucA1) enzyme can release fucose from glycoconjugates. This fucose is released from the lysosome into the cytosol, where it is acted on by salvage pathway enzymes (Armstrong et al., 2022), (Ng et al., 2023). The salvage pathway begins with the fucose kinase (FCSK, also known as FUK) enzyme phosphorylating fucose, resulting in an intermediate sugar

Fig. 3. An overview of the different pathways which can be used to synthesise GDP-fucose for fucosylation. In the *de novo* synthesis pathway, mannose is transported into the cell from the extracellular space, where it is converted to GDP-fucose, which itself is converted to GDP-fucose by the action of GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase (GMD) followed by GDP-fucose-synthase (FX). The salvage pathway, however, has two branches. It can derive free fucose from either the extracellular space or by the release of fucose from glycoconjugates in the lysosome with the α -L-fucosidase (FucA1) enzyme. This free fucose is then phosphorylated by fucose kinase (FCSK), with the resulting fucose-1-phosphate intermediate being converted to GDP-fucose by fucose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase (FPGT).

phosphate, fucose-1-phosphate, which is then converted into GDP-Fuc by fucose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase (FPGT). Loss of FCSK function results in a defective salvage pathway and severe congenital disorders (Ng et al., 2018). Most of the GDP-Fuc pool available to the FUTs comes from *de novo* synthesis (Becker and Lowe, 2003), (Skurska et al., 2022).

Research into fucosylation and the modulation of its metabolism has focused on two key enzymes involved in fucose's *de novo* synthesis: GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase (GMD) and GDP-fucose-synthase (FX, also known as GFUS) (Fig. 4). GMD catalyses the multistep conversion of GDP-Man into an intermediate keto species, GDP-4-keto-6-deoxy mannose (Pfeiffer et al., 2019). The structure of the human GMD protein and its β -elimination mechanism has been characterised at atomic resolution, providing a mechanistic understanding of this metabolic step which could be used in the targeted design of metabolic inhibitors. The mechanism of GMD involves three steps, an initial oxidation of GDP-Man at the C-4 carbon atom, the elimination of water, and finally, the NADPH-reduction at the C-6 position (Pfeiffer et al., 2019). Following

these GMD-mediated conversions, the FX protein, encoded by the Tissue-Specific Transplantation Antigen P35B (TSTA3) gene, catalyses the next steps in *de novo* fucose synthesis, involving a mechanism of epimerisation and reduction to form GDP-Fuc (Tonetti et al., 1996). Early research into the FX protein from *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) showed that the C-3 and C-5 carbon atoms of GDP-4-keto-6-deoxy mannose are epimerised by FX in two separate reactions, followed by an NADPH-dependent reduction of the carbonyl group at C-4 (Lau and Tanner, 2008). Two key residues in the *E. coli* FX protein, Cys109 and His179, function as a base and an acid in these two epimerisation reactions. The epimerisation has a precise order, starting with the C-3 atom, followed by C-5. These epimerisation reactions are then followed by the NADPH-dependent reduction of the C-4 carbonyl group into a hydroxyl group, resulting in GDP-Fuc formation (Lau and Tanner, 2008). The corresponding residues in the human FX protein are Cys116 and His186, which also function as a base and an acid, respectively, during each epimerisation step, followed by NADPH-reduction of the C-4 carbon, producing GDP-Fuc (Zhou et al., 2013). The resulting GDP-Fuc

Fig. 4. An overview of the *de novo* metabolic pathways for fucose and sialic acid synthesis. The *de novo* synthesis of fucose begins with mannose-6-phosphate, an intermediate phosphate metabolite derived from fructose-6-phosphate, a product of glycolysis. This sugar is converted to another phosphate intermediate, mannose-1-phosphate, which is converted to the activated nucleotide sugar GDP-Man. GDP-Man is the substrate of GMD, transforming it into GDP-4-keto-6-deoxy mannose, which is acted upon by the FX protein, producing activated GDP-Fucose. The SLC35C1 transporter transports GDP-fucose into the Golgi apparatus, where the FUT enzymes produce fucosylated glycans. Sialic acid synthesis begins with UDP-GlcNAc, the product of the hexosamine biosynthetic pathway, which is processed by the bifunctional GNE, which first converts UDP-GlcNAc into *N*-acetylmannosamine through its epimerase domain, and then phosphorylates ManNAc *N*-acetylmannosamine into *N*-acetylmannosamine-6-phosphate, with its kinase domain. NANS converts this into *N*-Acetylneuraminic acid-9-phosphate, which is dephosphorylated by NANP to produce free *N*-acetylneuraminic acid. This free sialic acid is then activated by the CMAS enzyme, coupling it with CMP, producing CMP-sialic acid. This activated nucleotide sugar precursor is transported into the Golgi by the SLC35A1 transporter, where the ST enzymes produce sialylated glycans. Abbreviations: HK: hexokinase, GPI: Glucose-6-phosphate isomerase, PMI: phosphomannose isomerase, PMM: phosphomannomutase, MPG: mannose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase, GDP-Man: guanosine diphosphate-mannose, GMD: GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase, FX: GDP-Fucose-synthase, GDP-Fuc: guanosine diphosphate-fucose, FUT: fucosyltransferase, UDP-GlcNAc: uridine diphosphate *N*-acetylglucosamine, GNE: UDP-*N*-acetylglucosamine 2 epimerase, ManNAc: *N*-acetylmannosamine, NANS: *N*-acetylneuraminic acid synthase, NANP: *N*-acetylneuraminic acid phosphatase, CMAS: cytidine monophosphate *N*-acetylneuraminic acid synthetase, ST: sialyltransferase.

metabolite is then transported to the Golgi, where it interacts with the 13 different FUT enzymes, producing fucosylated glycans with α 1-2, α 1-3 or α 1-6 linkages (Becker and Lowe, 2003). FX knockout systems have been developed to pursue fucosylated antibodies. A recent study examining FX KO in CHO cells demonstrated that the levels of GDP-Fuc and fucosylation were reduced, indicating that *de novo* fucose synthesis had been inhibited. When the culture medium of these cells was supplemented with fucose, fucosylation was restored, indicating that FX regulates the *de novo* synthesis of fucose and that when its function is disrupted, the salvage pathway becomes more prevalent in fucose metabolism (Prabhu et al., 2022). Further research has demonstrated that multiple pools of GDP-Fuc are available to the FUT enzymes, and cells can distinguish between GDP-Fuc from these pools before directing it towards specific fucose linkage types (Sosicka et al., 2022). This study examined four sources of fucose, and when fucose was added exogenously to cells at a concentration of between 30 and 50 μ M, the *de novo* synthesis of GDP-Fuc was suppressed, with exogenous fucose becoming the major source of the fucose found in the resulting *N*-glycans of secreted glycoproteins. The fucosylated *N*-glycans arising from glucose were more sensitive to changes in the supply of exogenous fucose than were *N*-glycans with a mannose origin. Exogenous fucose did not increase the total concentration of GDP-Fuc in the cells, suggesting that exogenous fucose triggers feedback inhibition of GMD. However, adding exogenous fucose reduced the salvage pathway and decreased it by only 10–40%, demonstrating that the cells can distinguish between GDP-Fuc from different sources. This research suggests that the GDP-Fuc is found in multiple pools and that cells can distinguish between these pools to select GDP-fucose of specific origins (Sosicka et al., 2022). Therefore, the metabolic flux regulating fucosylation is more dynamic than was previously thought, with multiple points of regulation arising from these distinct pools of GDP-Fuc.

This mechanistic research into fucosylation has demonstrated that the metabolic pools used to synthesise fucose can respond dynamically to environmental changes. This paves the way for designing targeted metabolic inhibitors, which show potential as novel glycotherapeutic approaches for treating inflammation. Understanding how the metabolic flux of activated monosaccharides regulates fucosylation is an important area to be examined in future research.

As discussed, glycan synthesis is a highly dynamic process. The pathways required for synthesising precursor monosaccharides depend upon the HBP pathway. This critical metabolic pathway provides the substrate for synthesising the UDP-GlcNAc and CMP-Neu5Ac monosaccharides, whilst mannose, partly derived from glucose, is used as a substrate for GDP-Man and GDP-Fuc. Glycosylation requires sufficient metabolic flux through these pathways to sustain healthy *N*-glycan synthesis. The complex interplay of these pathway networks is highly sensitive to environmental changes, as often occurs during inflammation. Many chronic diseases show altered expression of glycans, and recent work from our research group has revealed that changes in glycosylation expression play a major role in inflammation (Joyce et al., 2021), (Rebello et al., 2021) & (Ronan et al., 2022).

4. Inflammation directly impacts glycosylation

4.1. Inflammation induces metabolic dysfunction

Inflammation can induce profound changes in the glycosylation profiles of cells and tissues, with altered glycosylation also contributing to inflammatory pathogenesis (Reilly et al., 2019). Inflammation is also associated with changes in specific glycan types, such as sialic acid and fucose, and changes in these glycans can act as markers or 'glyco-signatures' of disease. Pathological conditions induce cell metabolic changes, regulating the switch between glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation. Inflammation induces metabolic reprogramming and a shift towards glycolysis, with increases in the expression of the transmembrane glucose transporter (GLUT) proteins and lactate. The

inflammatory expression of GLUTs, such as GLUT-1, leads to increases in glucose concentration in cells, along with the upregulation of glycolytic flux (Gallagher et al., 2020). This increase in glucose uptake is associated with elevated levels of proinflammatory cytokines and the proliferation of effector T cell subsets such as Th1, Th2 and Th17 cells, in contrast to regulatory T cells, which are promoted by oxidative phosphorylation and fatty acid oxidation (Michalek et al., 2011). Under inflammatory conditions, the expression of GLUTs and glycolytic enzymes is increased (Mochizuki et al., 2001). In work examining the corneal stroma of C57BL/6 mice infected with Herpes simplex virus by qRT-PCR, the expression of glycolytic genes (*HK2*, *PFKP* & *PFKFB3*), GLUT-1, GLUT-3 and MCT-4 were all increased in inflamed corneas compared with naïve corneas. Further immunofluorescence analysis of these proteins linked to glycolytic metabolism showed that GLUT-3 and MCT-4 were expressed in the stromal tissue of inflamed corneas, absent from the naïve corneas. These findings demonstrate the shift towards glucose uptake and glycolytic metabolism in inflammatory conditions (Rao and Suvas, 2019). Similar results were observed in a study analysing the metabolic profile of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) synovial tissue. GLUT-1 was highly expressed in the lining & sub-lining layers and the vasculature of RA synovial tissue, indicating an active glycolytic metabolism in this pathology. As well as this, when RA-synovial fibroblast cells (RASFCs) were treated with 3-(3-pyridinyl)-1-(4-pyridinyl)-2-propen-1-one (3PO), an inhibitor of glycolysis, inflammatory processes were reversed. 3PO effectively blocked toll-like receptor 2 induced migration, invasion, and cytokine production by the RASFCs (McGarry et al., 2017). These studies show that inflammation can induce profound metabolic shifts, with a shift towards glycolysis.

4.2. Inflammation induces global changes in *N*-glycosylation

Alterations in HBP flux regulates *N*-glycosylation by providing UDP-GlcNAc, influencing the amount of glycosylation that occurs and the types of glycan structures synthesised. In a TGF- β induced model of the tumorigenic epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) process in A549 lung cancer cells, the metabolic and glycosylation profiles of the cells were altered (Lucena et al., 2016). The levels and activity of the rate-limiting enzymes GFAT and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) for critical carbohydrate metabolic pathways, the HBP, and the pentose phosphate pathway, respectively, were analysed by Western blotting and enzyme activity assays. TGF- β induced EMT triggered increases in the levels and activity of GFAT, along with a decrease in G6PD, indicating that glucose was being shunted through the HBP. Along with this, the level of UDP-GlcNAc was increased with EMT. This activation of HBP flux also led to increases in glycosylation, as measured by glycan-binding lectin proteins. Fucosylated, poly-LacNAc-containing, and sialylated glycans increased in the TGF- β treated cells (Lucena et al., 2016). Each glycan is associated with inflammation, indicating that modulation of key metabolic pathways, such as the HBP alters glycosylation. An analysis of inflammatory bowel disease provides further evidence of the links between products of the HBP and glycosylation (Dias et al., 2018). Mucosal T cells were isolated from ulcerative colitis (UC) patients and supplemented with GlcNAc, promoting the activation of the HBP and increasing the branching of *N*-glycans on the T cell receptor (TCR) protein. This increase in β 1,6-GlcNAc branched *N*-glycan enhanced the ability of the TCR to regulate T cell activation, resulting in a downregulation of inflammation. Similar results were observed in *in vivo* experiments, with the chemical induction of colitis in mice by oral or rectal administration of dextran sodium sulfate. UC was induced in wild-type mice and in mice which were null or heterozygous for the *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase 5 (*MGAT5*) gene, which is responsible for the formation of branched *N*-glycan structures. In the *MGAT5* null or heterozygous mice, the onset of colitis occurred earlier and was more severe than in the wild-type mice. Induced colitis caused an infiltration of CD3-expressing lymphocytes into the intestinal lamina propria, while GlcNAc supplementation caused an increase in β 1,6 branched glycans in

the tissue. Along with this, the glycan branching on the TCR protein of intestinal T cells was increased, while the severity and progression of the disease were reduced in the *MGAT5* null or heterozygous mice (Dias et al., 2018). These results demonstrate that *N*-glycan branching is finely controlled and that the dysregulation of the enzymes regulating this branching process is involved in inflammation. Further evidence of the links between EMT, the HBP and *N*-glycosylation has been uncovered in the synthesis of extracellular matrix (ECM). In human small airway epithelial cells, which underwent TGF- β induced EMT, *N*-glycosylation was increased. When the targets for this EMT-induced *N*-glycosylation were analysed, the glycosylation of ECM proteins was found to be highly upregulated. As well as this, EMT triggered the upregulation of HBP flux, as indicated by an increase in UDP-GlcNAc (Zhang et al., 2019). Complementing these studies examining the upregulation of branching during inflammation, recent research has also shown that increased branching can be identified using methods such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) from patient samples such as plasma. GlycA is an NMR biomarker associated with high levels of GlcNAc on inflammatory, acute-phase proteins. In an analysis of plasma samples from 87 individuals, this GlycA NMR signal was directly associated with the levels of bi-, tri- and tetra-antennary branched glycans, showing that GlycA and *N*-glycan branching could act as a biomarker for inflammatory hyperglycosylation (Noel et al., 2023).

4.3. Inflammatory *N*-glycosylation in cancer

As discussed, inflammation is associated with the dysregulation of *N*-glycosylation. As inflammation is also one of the hallmarks of cancer, it is not surprising that changes in glycosylation are involved in the inflammatory pathogenesis of various types of cancer, with altered expression of glycosyltransferase enzymes resulting in profound changes in glycan profiles (Tvaroška, 2022). Glycosylation, therefore, is a nexus for inflammation and cancer metabolism, as will be discussed in this section. For example, the regulation of glycosylation by metabolic flux through the HBP was demonstrated in research analysing KRAS mutations in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cells (Ricciardiello et al., 2021). In this study, the metabolism of a KRAS mutant PDAC cell line (MIA PaCa-2) was profiled by Seahorse analysis and compared with KRAS wild-type BxPC-3 cells. The MIA PaCa-2 cells showed increased extracellular acidification rate, oxygen consumption rate, and ATP production, indicating increased dependence of KRAS mutant cells on glycolysis and increased metabolic activity. As well as this, the KRAS mutant cells showed increased HBP flux, as measured by elevated protein *O*-GlcNAcylation. These data suggested that the KRAS mutant MIA PaCa-2 cells were more dependent on increased flux through glycolysis and the HBP. To investigate the role of glycosylation in this process, MIA PaCa-2 and BxPC-3 cells were treated with 2-deoxyglucose (2-DG), which inhibits the HBP and *N*-glycosylation, with their glycan profiles and cell survival rates subsequently analysed. The PHA (*Phaseolus Vulgaris*) lectin was used to analyse the presence of branched, tri- and tetra-antennary *N*-glycan structures and Trypan blue to measure survival. 2-DG treatment led to a significant decrease (~70%) in PHA staining in the MIA PaCa-2 cells, compared with a ~34% reduction in the BxPC-3 cells. 2-DG treatment also caused a significant reduction in cell survival in the MIA PaCa-2 cells compared with the BxPC-3 cells. When these cells were treated with 2-DG and mannose, the decrease in PHA staining was abolished, and in the KRAS mutant PaCa-2 cells, cell survival was increased significantly (Ricciardiello et al., 2021). These results show that increased HBP flux is a characteristic marker of pathology in these KRAS mutant cells. By inhibiting the increased glycosylation associated with the HBP, oncogenic cell survival will be reduced.

Mechanistic links between glycosylation and metabolism and cancer have also been profiled in hyperglycemic conditions. In a study analysing the effects of hyperglycemia on colon cancer, it was demonstrated that high glucose treatment induced aberrant glycosylation via upregulation of HBP flux and GFAT activity and promoted growth and

invasiveness of tumours (Vasconcelos-Dos-Santos et al., 2017). Murine colon cancer cells (MC38) were grown in both low glucose and high glucose conditions, and their glycosylation profiles were subsequently analysed by lectin histochemistry. The high glucose treatments caused an increase in highly mannosylated, sialylated, and fucosylated glycans. High glucose was also shown to activate metabolic flux through the HBP, as indicated by increased UDP-GlcNAc. As well as this, when adenocarcinoma and surrounding normal tissue from colon cancer patients were analysed, the mRNA and protein levels of GFAT1 and GFAT2 were upregulated in the adenocarcinoma (Vasconcelos-Dos-Santos et al., 2017). Further work from the same group, which also studied MC38 colon cancer cells, provided more details on the glycosylation-relevant metabolic changes induced by the high glucose treatment (Loponte et al., 2022). When liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis was carried out on the metabolites produced by these cells, the substrate pool of activated monosaccharides such as GDP-Man, GDP-Fuc and CMP-Neu5Ac, along with an increase in intracellular glucose, were detected. When the glycosylation profiles of these high glucose-conditioned MC38 cells were analysed, increased amounts of *N*-glycans were observed, with this difference being most prominent in the hybrid glycans. Hybrid-type glycans that were fucosylated, sialylated or contained fucose and sialic acid were increased in the high-glucose cells (Loponte et al., 2022). As well as this, increases in the concentration of specific glycosylation metabolites can be tracked to monitor the progression of the disease. A mouse xenograft model of glioblastoma (GBM) examining changes in fucose metabolism showed hyperactivation of the fucose metabolic pathway. In an untargeted metabolomic analysis of the xenografts, a significant increase in the levels of the GDP-Fuc metabolite was observed. Positron emission tomography analysis of a radiolabelled analogue of fucose, 6-[¹⁸F] fluoro-L-fucose, was also carried out in these mice to measure fucosylation. This analysis revealed an accumulation of fucose in the xenografts (Pieri et al., 2023). These results demonstrate that pathological changes induce alterations in metabolic flux through the HBP, which in turn drive aberrant glycosylation, influencing the progression of inflammatory cancer.

4.4. Inflammation induces changes in sialylation

Notable early results demonstrating the role of sialylation in inflammation came from an experimental turpentine oil-induced mouse inflammation model (Yasukawa et al., 2005). The serum glycoproteins of mice injected subcutaneously with turpentine oil were examined by sialic acid binding lectin proteins, MAA (*Maackia Amurensis*) & SSA (*Sambucus Sieboldiana*) and the monoclonal antibody 2-4B (mAb.2-4B), which bind to α 2,3, α 2,6 & α 2,8 linked Neu5Ac respectively. Inflammation increased all three of these sialic acids in glycans from the serum of turpentine oil-injected mice. RT-PCR also analysed the expression of mRNAs encoding a range of ST enzymes for further evidence of inflammatory sialylation. The mRNA expression of the sialyltransferases ST3Gal I, ST3Gal III, ST6GalNAc VI & ST6Gal I was increased in the livers of inflamed mice (Yasukawa et al., 2005). These results provided early evidence that sialic acid is upregulated during inflammation and that sialylation can act as a glycosignature of disease. They have been further supported by work on the effect of inflammation on sialylation. In one mouse inflammation model, mice were treated with the pro-inflammatory compound chlorite-oxidised oxyamylose (COAM). The COAM-injected mice showed significant increases in the sialylation and branching of serum glycans, as shown by hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography high-performance liquid chromatography analysis of glycans released from mouse serum samples.

Along with this, the expression of the ST3Gal I ST enzyme was increased in the livers of mice treated with pro-inflammatory COAM (Saldova et al., 2013). This link between increased sialylation and inflammation was also observed in an animal model of spinal cord injury. Using a spinal cord transection model in rats, lectin staining with the SNA-I (*Sambucus nigra*), which binds to α 2,6 linked Neu5Ac, was

carried out. In the transected spinal cords, increased SNA-I immunoreactivity was observed, indicating an upregulation in sialic acid. Co-staining for CD11b, a marker for macrophage and microglia immune cells, was performed to determine if this increased sialylation was linked to inflammation. CD11b+ macrophages and microglia were detected at the transection sites and were colocalised with SNA-I immunofluorescence (Ronan et al., 2022). These results show that hypersialylation is associated with inflammation in spinal cord injury, a marker which could serve as a glycosignature of this debilitating pathology.

The roles of metabolic pathways feeding into the synthesis of sialic acid glycans have also been profiled in cancer, where inflammation also plays a significant role. Sialic acid metabolic pathways are linked to the HBP through the bifunctional GNE enzyme (Teoh et al., 2018). The mechanistic connections between the HBP and sialic acid synthesis have been investigated in breast cancer, revealing that the flux of the CMP-Neu5Ac metabolite regulates breast cancer progression and metastasis. When the metabolite levels of breast cancer cell lines were analysed, CMP-Neu5Ac levels were highest in the highly metastatic 4T1 cells, compared with the slightly metastatic 4T07 and non-metastatic 67NR cells. These findings were confirmed with an analysis of UDP-GlcNAc, Neu5Ac and CMP-Neu5Ac by ¹³C-Glucose isotope labelling, which again showed that the 4T1 cells had the highest flux through sialic acid metabolism.

Along with CMP-Neu5Ac, two of the key enzymes in sialic acid metabolism were shown to modulate breast cancer pathology; GNE and CMAS, which catalyses the activation of sialic acid into CMP-Neu5Ac. When the expression of the GNE and CMAS genes were analysed with patient survival data using Kaplan-Meier survival curves, the expression of both enzymes was highly associated with reduced survival. In support of these data were *in vivo* experiments involving the orthotopic injection of wild-type 4T1 cells and CMAS KO 4T1 cells into mice. The area of lung metastases was reduced in the CMAS-KO injected mice relative to the CMAS-WT injected mice, with these CMAS-KO mice also showing a reduction in the number of discrete lung metastases (Teoh et al., 2018). Further work demonstrating the role of sialic acid metabolism and CMAS has been carried out in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), which compared the sialylation and metabolic profiles of highly malignant BPLER and less aggressive HMLER TNBC cell lines. When the metabolites produced by these two cell lines were analysed by ¹³C-¹H NMR, the BPLER cells were found to have increased levels of sialic acid (Neu5Ac) compared to the HMLER. The sialylation of these cells was also compared, using lectin histochemistry with the WGA (*Wheat germ agglutinin*) lectin, which binds to sialic acid. The highly malignant BPLER cells were more heavily sialylated than the HMLER cells. Along with this increase in sialic acid, the critical metabolic enzyme involved in sialic acid synthesis, CMAS was upregulated in the highly malignant BPLER cells and was not detected in the HMLER cells (O'Day et al., 2018).

4.5. Inflammation induces changes in fucosylation

Inflammation also induces changes in fucosylation, with immune cells upregulating the expression and activity of the FUT enzymes during inflammatory pathogenesis. A study examining the role of fucosylation in RA found that the FUT expression was upregulated (Li et al., 2014). In synovial tissue samples from RA patients, the expression of the genes encoding FUT1, FUT2, FUT4, FUT5, FUT6, FUT7 and FUT9 increased. The *SLC35C1* gene encoding the GDP-Fuc transport protein was upregulated in these inflamed tissue samples, further supporting the positive correlation between fucosylation and inflammation. These FUTs were also expressed primarily by the proinflammatory M1 macrophages. The expression of these FUT enzymes increased by 5–10-fold in the macrophages, which differentiated to the M1 phenotype, compared with their precursor monocytes. Furthermore, their expression levels correlated with the levels of the gene encoding the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α (Li et al., 2014). Fucosylation also plays an important role in neuroinflammation, influencing the activity of the microglial cells involved in

the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease (AD) (Jin et al., 2023). Microglia can be activated by aggregates of amyloid β peptides (A β), resulting in the secretion of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6. Recent work has demonstrated that A β -induced activation of microglia is associated with an increase in the expression of FUT8 and the levels of core fucosylation. When quantitative PCR analysis was carried out on the brains of human AD patients and in brains from 5xFAD mice, a mouse model of AD, FUT8 transcription was increased relative to respective controls. Flow cytometry experiments with human induced pluripotent stem cells derived microglia (hiMG) were also carried out to measure core fucosylation. When the hiMG were treated with either lipopolysaccharides toxin or oligomers of the A β peptide, AAL lectin binding was increased, indicating upregulation in core fucosylation (Jin et al., 2023).

In an *in vitro* model of IVD inflammation with nucleus pulposus (NP) cells, fucosylation was again shown to be upregulated in inflammation. Treatment with IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6 cytokines triggered significant increases in fucosylation, as indicated by lectin immunofluorescence with the fucose binding lectins, AAL (*Aleuria aurantia*) (α 1,6-Fuc) and UEA-I (*Ulex europaeus* agglutinin I) which bind to glycans containing α 1,6 Fuc & α 1,2 Fuc respectively. This inflammatory hyperfucosylation was also associated with metabolic dysfunction (Joyce et al., 2021). These data indicate that fucosylation regulates key signalling pathways in activating immune cells such as macrophages and microglia and that hyperfucosylation is associated with inflammation. Once they are well characterised, these changes can act as glycosignatures of disease.

The studies described here demonstrate mechanistic links between inflammation and the dysregulation of glycosylation, particularly hypersialylation and hyperfucosylation. Inflammation can induce changes in the critical enzymes regulating glycan synthesis, glycan transporter proteins, glycan precursor metabolites and downstream glycosylation levels. In recent years, there has been extensive development of inhibitors modulating the activity of critical enzymes in these metabolic pathways, allowing researchers to examine their roles in inflammatory hypersialylation and hyperfucosylation. As discussed in the following sections, these glycosylation inhibitors can serve as valuable tools in research and pave the way towards future glycotherapies.

5. Modulation of glycosylation

5.1. Modulation of glycosylation by inhibitors

Glycosylation can be modulated by using inhibitors targeting the key enzymes involved in their metabolism. Using these inhibitors allows researchers to profile the relative contribution of the various glycan synthesis enzymes to the glycans' metabolic flux. As well as this, glycan inhibitors have the potential to be used in inflammation as glycotherapies (Dwek et al., 2002), (Almahayni et al., 2022). An overview of metabolic inhibitors of glycosylation is presented in Table 1. Tunicamycin is a nucleoside antibiotic commonly used in research to inhibit N-glycosylation by blocking the transfer of UDP-GlcNAc to the Dol-P precursor lipid. This inhibitor comprises a uracil base, linked to a tunicamine sugar, which itself is bound to GlcNAc, along with an aliphatic fatty tail. Tunicamycin acts as a high-affinity competitive inhibitor of DPAGT1, which transfers UDP-GlcNAc, allowing it to block N-glycosylation (Yoo et al., 2018) (Table 1). Inhibition of glycosylation targeting the HBP has been investigated in multiple cancer types, where glycosylation plays different roles in several steps of tumour progression, regulating tumour proliferation, invasion, metastasis and angiogenesis (Dennis et al., 2009), (Lynch and Reginato, 2011). Two widely studied inhibitors targeting the rate-limiting HBP enzyme GFAT1 are azaserine and 6-diazo-5-oxo-L-norleucine (DON). Both residues are glutamine analogues suppressing GFAT, thereby limiting GlcNAc generation of the HBP in cells. Azaserine inhibits purine synthesis and pathways utilising glutamine (Bennett et al., 1956). Azaserine can be used to target the HBP by inhibiting the GFAT enzyme, which has

Table 1
Metabolic inhibitors of glycosylation and their modes of action.

Inhibitor	Target	Mode of action	References
2-deoxy-D-glucose	Glycolysis, HBP	Glucose mimic blocks the action of glucose-6-phosphate isomerase	Ricciardiello et al. (2021)
Tunicamycin	N-Glycosylation	UDP-GlcNAc mimic blocking GlcNAc phosphotransferase, thereby inhibiting the transfer of UDP-GlcNAc to dol-P	Yoo et al. (2018)
Azaserine	HBP GFAT	Glutamine analogue inhibiting GFAT enzyme activity	Bennett et al. (1956), Chen et al. (2019)
6-diazo-5-oxo-L-norleucine (DON)	HBP GFAT	Glutamine analogue inhibiting GFAT enzyme activity	Chen et al. (2017), Sharma et al. (2019)
FR054	PGM3	GlcNAc-6-P mimetic preventing PGM3 enzyme activity	Ricciardiello et al. (2018)
Ac ₄ Glc2Bz	HBP	GlcNAc mimic blocking several proteins and enzymes in the HBP pathway	Saeui et al. (2023)
Sialylation Inhibitors			
3F _{ax} -Neu5Ac	Sialic acid Neu-5Ac	Fluorinated Neu-5Ac analogue acting as a competitive inhibitor of sialyltransferase enzymes	Rillahan et al. (2012), Büll et al. (2013), Joyce et al. (2021)
C-5 carbamate fluorinated sialic acids	Sialic acid Neu-5Ac	Modified fluorinated Neu-5Ac analogues, which are metabolised by CMAS into active inhibitors that act on GNE & sialyltransferase enzymes	Heise et al. (2019), Moons et al. (2022), van Scherpenzeel et al. (2022)
C-6 selenium Man-NAc	Neu5-Ac, GNE	C-6 modified ManNAc analogue blocking GNE/MNK activity, inhibiting Neu5Ac synthesis from ManNAc	Nieto-Garcia et al. (2016)
C-3 Peracetylated 2-Acetylamino-2-deoxy-3-O-methyl-D-mannose	Neu5-Ac, GNE	C-3 modified ManNAc analogue blocking GNE/MNK activity, inhibiting Neu5Ac synthesis from ManNAc	Wrtil et al. (2014)
Fucosylation inhibitors			
2F-peracetyl fucose	Fucosylation, FUTs	Fluorinated fucose analogue, inhibiting FUT activity	Rillahan et al. (2012)
5-Thiofucose	Fucosylation, FUTs	Metabolised into GDP-5-T-Fuc, blocking FUT activity, subsequent accumulation leads to feedback inhibition of FUT activity	Zandberg et al. (2012)
Sulfonamide GDP-Fucose mimics	Fucosylation, FUT8	Binds to and inhibits the activity of FUT8	Manabe et al. (2017)
6-Alknyl-fucose	Fucosylation, FX	Inhibits the formation of GDP-Fuc by competitive inhibition of FX	Kizuka et al. (2017) Jin et al. (2023)
6,6,6-trifluoro-Fucose (Fucostatin I, II)	Fucosylation, GMD	Allosteric inhibition of GMD	Allen et al. (2016)
Fucotrim I, II	Fucosylation, GMD	Rhamnose 1-phosphate derivatives accumulate intracellularly, competitively inhibiting GMD	Pijnenborg et al. (2021)

therapeutic potential in cancer (Chen et al., 2019). DON has been investigated as a potential glycosylation inhibitor through interference with GFAT, one study found that in PDAC cells, addition of DON to cells induced proliferation arrest, alterations in epidermal growth factor receptor EGFR and redox enzymes expression, and reduced cancer treatment resistance (Chen et al., 2017). Another study showed that DON treatment of PDAC increases antitumor activity and remodels the ECM to promote cytotoxic T cell and CD68+ macrophage infiltration in the tumour microenvironment. Furthermore, the study showed a decrease in HA and ECM in DON treated tumours transplanted in C57BL/6 mice following HBP inhibition by DON. Additionally, DON treatment sensitizes tumours to anti-PD1 therapy which, together with the increased presence of CD8+ T cells within the tumour, improves the tumour response to anti-PD1 therapy (Sharma et al., 2019). PGM3 is another enzyme in the HBP which can be targeted by inhibitors. The FR054 inhibitor mimics GlcNAc-6-P, the substrate for PGM3. FR054 is more sensitive than azaserine and DON treatment, blocking both *de novo* synthesis and the salvage pathway of GlcNAc by inhibiting PGM3 activity which converts GlcNAc-6-P to GlcNAc-1-P. FR054, acting as a competitive inhibitor of PGM3, can induce a decrease of intracellular UDP-GlcNAc, resulting in a reduction of complex branched N-glycans. Furthermore, treatment of breast cancer cells with FR054 induced cell proliferation arrest and apoptosis, as well as a reduction in metastatic MDA-MB-231 cells adhesion and migration. Additionally, FR054 induces ER stress and accumulation of unfolded proteins within cells activates the unfolded protein response. (Ricciardiello et al., 2018). Another inhibitor of HBP flux is Ac₄Glc2Bz, a mimetic of GlcNAc modified with a benzyl group and peracetylation (Saeui et al., 2023). This modified structure was designed to target a range of proteins and enzymes involved in the HBP, including the GLUTs, HK and GFAT. When GBM cells were treated with Ac₄Glc2Bz, the production of UDP-GlcNAc was reduced substantially, and the overall glucose metabolism of these cells was also altered. As well as this, treatment with the HBP inhibitor reduced the motility of the GBM cells, demonstrating the potential of glycotherapies in this pathology (Saeui et al., 2023). These modulators of glycosylation act at a systemic level, disrupting the metabolic pathways which feed into the synthesis of all types of glycans. However, inhibitors targeting specific types of glycosylation, such as fucosylation or sialylation, have also been developed and show therapeutic potential, as will be discussed further.

5.2. Modulation of sialylation by inhibitors

Sialic acid inhibitors have allowed for detailed analysis of the metabolic steps specific to sialic acid metabolism. 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac is a 3-fluoro analogue of sialic acid, which cells can easily take up due to peracetylation (Table 1). Once inside the cells, this analogue acts as a competitive inhibitor of STs. Upon treatment with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, cells deacetylate the inhibitor with esterase enzymes, and the production of natural CMP-Neu5Ac is halted as CMAS instead synthesises the corresponding nucleotide sugar CMP-3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. When this nucleotide sugar derivative of the inhibitor accumulates in the cell, it leads to the competitive inhibition of the STs (Rillahan et al., 2012). The 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac inhibitor of sialylation has been used as a research tool and has also shown possible therapeutic potential. In research into Parkinson's Disease (PD), 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac was used in a functional study to show how inhibition of sialylation contributes to metabolic dysfunction, changes in the characteristic glycosylation profile of rat embryonic precursor cells to the dopaminergic ventral mesencephalon, increased ER stress along with reduced inflammation. The researchers in this study used this inhibitor to probe precisely a series of molecular events involved in this pathology, analysing the role of glycosylation (Rebelo et al., 2022b). Early work on the therapeutic application of sialylation inhibition examined its effects on tumour suppression. This study investigated the effects of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac on mouse tumour sialylation in a B16-F10 model of melanoma. 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment resulted in a reduction in cancer

cell migration and adhesion *in vitro* and limited the growth of tumour cells *in vivo*. This inhibition of sialic acid also reduced the tumour's immunosuppressive environment, enabling CD8+ T cells to suppress tumour growth (Büll et al., 2013). Further work showed again that intratumoural injections of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac could reduce tumour growth and sialylation of the tumour mass in the B16-F10 mouse model. This was shown to occur through a CD8+ T cell mediated mechanism.

When tumours were treated with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, their immune cell populations were altered, increasing CD4+, CD8+ T cells and natural killer immune cells. Tumour growth reduction in the 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac-treated tumours was mediated by the CD8+ T cells (Büll et al., 2018). Similarly, in an *in vitro* model of inflammation of the IVD, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment was effective in blocking cytokine-induced inflammation. When NP cells were treated with IL-1 β , TNF- α and IL-6, there were increases in sialylation, as indicated by lectin histochemistry with the MAA and SNA-I lectins, which bind to α 2,3 and α 2,6 linked Neu5Ac respectively. 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac was effective in blocking this inflammatory hypersialylation. This sialic acid inhibition also reduced the expression of catabolic enzymes and ameliorated metabolic dysfunction in these cytokine-treated NP cells (Joyce et al., 2021). These studies demonstrate the immunomodulatory effects of sialylation inhibition and the potential of this glycotherapeutic approach to inflammation, which will be described further with examples of inhibitors targeting key enzymes in

the metabolic pathways underlying sialylation and fucosylation.

As CMAS is a key enzyme that is involved in processing metabolic sialic acid inhibitors, converting them into corresponding CMP-bound derivatives, understanding how they interact with CMAS is important to developing more effective inhibition approaches. One study compared the effectiveness of 3-fluorinated sialic acid inhibitors, in which the natural C-5 N-acetamide group was replaced by carbamate or amide groups (Heise et al., 2019). The conversion of C-5 carbamate-modified sialic acid inhibitors or C-5 amide analogues into their respective CMP derivatives was compared. In experiments with B16-F10 mouse tumour cells, the carbamate-based metabolic inhibitors were found to be more readily metabolised to their CMP derivatives by the CMAS enzyme, with improved inhibition of sialylation. Modelling experiments were carried out between these inhibitors and the structure of CMAS, indicating that the carbamate-modified inhibitors had increased binding interactions with the hydrophilic binding pocket of CMAS, enhancing their inhibitory capacity. These results showed that treatment with the C-5 carbamate-based inhibitors led to increased production of their respective CMP-bound derivatives, which resulted in higher concentrations of the active sialic acid inhibitor, which could inhibit the downstream GNE and STs (Fig. 5) (Heise et al., 2019). Further work on these 3-fluoro sialic acid inhibitors compared the effects of substituting the natural C-5 N-acetamide group for a range of alternative chemical

Fig. 5. Modulation of fucose and sialic acid metabolism through inhibitors targeting key enzymes. Inhibitors of fucosylation target GMD, the FX protein and the FUT enzymes. The Fucostatin and Fucotrim inhibitors target GMD, with Fucostatin inhibiting GMD by binding to an allosteric site, while Fucotrim competitively inhibits GMD. 6-Alkynyl fucose acts on the FX enzyme by competitive inhibition, while the 2F-peracetyl fucose, 5-thio fucose and the sulfonamide-modified versions of fucose inhibit the action of the FUTs. Metabolic inhibitors of sialylation target GNE, CMAS and the ST enzymes. Analogues of N-acetylmannosamine (ManNAc) modified at the C-3, or C-6 atom positions target the bifunctional GNE enzyme. Modified versions of sialic acid inhibit the action of the STs. Abbreviations: GMD: GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase, FX: GDP-Fucose synthase, FUT: fucosyltransferase, GNE: UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2 epimerase, CMAS: N-acetylneuramate cytidylyltransferase, ST: sialyltransferase.

groups, as well as C-4, C-8 & C-9 modifications. The derivatives of these inhibitors each had varying efficacies, with the majority being more effective than the original 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac inhibitor, with the C-5 carbamate derivatives being the most effective, followed in order by S-thiocarbamate, thiourea, urea, and amide. Modifications of the C-4 also showed inhibitory potential, with either an azide or propargyloxycarbonyl group being substituted into the C-4 position or dual modifications with a C-4 azide and a C-5 carbamate. When the glycerol side chain in the sialic acid inhibitors was truncated, their inhibitory capacity was reduced in a length-dependent manner. However, when the C-5 groups of these truncated-glycerol inhibitors were converted to carbamate, inhibition was restored (Moons et al., 2022). These results demonstrate that the molecular structure of the sialic acid analogues used to inhibit CMAS and sialylation can be tailored to improve their inhibitory capacity and to increase the scope of available inhibitors.

A further study involving dynamic tracing of nucleotide sugars molecules analysed the steps in sialic acid metabolism, which the 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac inhibitor targets (van Scherpenzeel et al., 2022). After B16-F10 mouse melanoma cells were treated with peracetylated 3F_{ax}-NeuNAC, CMP-3F_{ax}-NeuNAC was synthesised, with maximum levels reached at 24 h, while the levels of endogenous CMP-NeuNAC metabolites were nearly depleted by 24 h. As well as this, the levels of ManNac-6-P, a sugar-phosphate intermediate metabolite, were reduced. This indicates that 3F_{ax}-NeuNAC acts by inhibiting GNE, with UDP-GlcNAc accumulating in the cell and its conversion into ManNac-6-P being reduced. In the treated cells, 3F_{ax}-NeuNAC was metabolised to CMP-3F_{ax}-NeuNAC, competing with the endogenous NeuNac metabolites, leading to feedback inhibition of GNE (Fig. 5). To further analyse the targeting of GNE in this mechanism of sialic acid inhibition, experiments were carried out with fibroblasts from a patient with French-type sialuria, a rare genetic disease resulting from mutations in the allosteric site of GNE. These GNE mutations lead to substantial increases in sialic acid production and the build-up of free sialic acid in the cytoplasm. Sialuria and control fibroblasts were treated with 3F_{ax}-NeuNAC. The control fibroblasts synthesised CMP-3F_{ax}-NeuNAC and decreased the production of endogenous CMP-NeuNAC and ManNac-6-P, as observed in the B16-F10 cells. In the Sialuria fibroblasts, however, there was slower CMP-3F_{ax}-NeuNAC synthesis and no effect on the levels of ManNac-6-P. These Sialuria results and analysis of metabolites in the B16-F10 melanoma cells show that CMP-3F_{ax}-NeuNAC causes allosteric inhibition of GNE (van Scherpenzeel et al., 2022).

Another approach for metabolic inhibition of sialylation is using modified *N*-acetylmannosamine analogues, which act as competitive inhibitors of the kinase domain (MNK) of the bifunctional GNE enzyme. Peracetylated 2-Acetyl-2-deoxy-3-*O*-methyl-D-mannose, a C-3 modified analogue of ManNac, is a notable example of an inhibitor targeting GNE (Wrtil et al., 2014). This small molecule inhibitor, one of the first membrane-permeable inhibitors of GNE, enters the cell and is then acted upon by esterase enzymes producing a non-peracetylated sugar. This resulting sugar binds to and inhibits the MNK domain of GNE. When Jurkat T cells were treated with the inhibitor, cell surface sialylation was measured by the PSL (*Polyporus squamosus*) lectin, and the concentrations of free, CMP-bound and membrane-bound Neu5Ac were decreased in cell lysates, indicating its efficacy in preventing sialylation (Wrtil et al., 2014). Following this, another study compared the inhibition of GNE/MNK with a range of selenium and sulphur-based C-6 derivatives of ManNac. These derivatives had selenium or sulphur replacing the position of the oxygen atom at C-6, blocking the binding pocket of the kinase domain. A C-6 ManNac diselenide dimer was the strongest kinase inhibitor from the panel of compounds tested (Fig. 5) (Nieto-Garcia et al., 2016). These inhibitors provide an alternative approach to the inhibition of sialylation, targeting the metabolic steps mediated by GNE, which direct ManNac into sialic acid synthesis, as opposed to the modified CMP-analogues that inhibit CMAS.

5.3. Modulation of fucosylation by inhibitors

Mimics of GDP-Fuc, the nucleotide sugar used by the FUT enzymes, have been developed as inhibitors of fucosylation (Table 1). An early version of this approach resulted in a GDP analogue with a GDP-alkyne core linked to azide molecules by copper-catalysed click chemistry. This mimic was shown to selectively inhibit the activity of FUT6, with limited activity against FUT3 or FUT5 (Lee et al., 2003). However, as this compound is anionic, with limited membrane permeability, a non-ionic GDP-mimic composed of an alkyne group coupled to a sulfonyl azide has been developed. These sulphonamide structures mimic the diphosphate group in the natural GDP-Fuc, which is important in the binding to FUT8. When these compounds were tested against FUT8, they were shown to effectively inhibit enzyme activity at a concentration of 100 μ M. The non-ionic nature of this inhibitor makes it more versatile than previous attempts at GDP-Fuc mimics, opening up the possibility of *in vivo* applications (Fig. 5) (Manabe et al., 2017).

FX and GMD are critical regulators of fucose metabolism, so they have emerged as key targets in developing metabolic fucosylation inhibitors. Fluorinated fucose analogues have been developed to inhibit fucosylation, which targets different proteins in fucosylation, from FX & GMD to the FUT enzymes. 2F-peracetyl fucose (2F-PAF) is a general fucosylation inhibitor that targets the FUT enzymes that catalyse the final steps in fucosylation. The cells take up the fluorinated and peracetylated fucose analogue and use the salvage pathway, resulting in the formation of the corresponding nucleotide sugar, GDP-2F-PAF, and the competitive inhibition of FUTs (Rillahan et al., 2012). In a recent study examining the *in vivo* efficacy of 2-deoxy-2-fluoro-L-Fucose (2-fluoro fucose, 2FF), treatment with this inhibitor blocked core fucosylation in a preclinical mouse model of GBM. In this mouse model, hyperfucosylation was shown to be characteristic of the pathology and was identified as a therapeutic target. 2FF-mediated inhibition of core fucosylation resulted in the reduction of tumour growth and the volume of GBM xenografts in the mice, demonstrating the therapeutic potential of fucose inhibition (Pieri et al., 2023). The first human trial of metabolic inhibitors of glycosylation was also recently carried out with a Phase I clinical trial of SGN-2FF, a variant of 2F-Fuc. Oral doses of 2 g – 15 g of SGN-2FF were given to patients with advanced-stage solid tumours. Metabolic fucose inhibition resulted in targeted inhibition of fucosylation, along with some preliminary anti-tumour activity, before the trial was cancelled due to thromboembolic events (Do et al., 2021). Despite the termination of this trial, the signs of efficacy in reducing fucosylation in humans and efficacy in treating the underlying disease show the potential for further exploring these metabolic inhibitors. 5-thiofucose (5T-Fuc) is an alternative metabolic inhibitor of fucosylation which targets the FUT enzymes. In experiments with HepG2 cells, 5T-Fuc was taken up by cells and then metabolised by the salvage pathway into an inhibitory GDP-5T-Fuc metabolite. As the FUT enzymes cannot utilise GDP-5T-Fuc, its accumulation leads to a decrease in the GDP-Fuc pool, feedback inhibition of these transferases and the inhibition of fucosylation (Zandberg et al., 2012). Another fucosylation inhibitor, 6-Alkynyl-fucose (6-Alk-Fuc), targets FX through competitive inhibition upon binding to its catalytic pocket. 6-Alk-Fuc treatment reduces the pool of available GDP-Fuc, inhibiting fucosylation, specifically the metabolic step mediated by FX (Kizuka et al., 2017). 6-Alk-Fuc has been combined with 2FF in an *in vitro* model of AD neuroinflammation. When hiMG cells were treated with pro-inflammatory A β oligomers, the reactivity of core-fucose-binding lectin proteins was increased. This core-fucosylation was reduced when these cells were co-treated with 2FF and 6-Alk-Fuc. This co-treatment with fucosylation inhibitors also showed therapeutic effects in response to this induced inflammation, with a reduction in the expression of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β & TNF- α . The inflamed hiMG cells also exhibited impaired phagocytosis, which was ameliorated by treatment with the two fucosylation inhibitors (Jin et al., 2023). Therapeutic effects of FX inhibition have, therefore, been shown in a model of inflammatory pathology. This

demonstrates the promise of inhibitors targeting key enzymes in fucose metabolism, an approach which can be examined further in other inflammatory diseases.

To target the metabolic step mediated by GMD, inhibitors derived from 6,6,6-trifluoro-Fuc (Fucostatin I and II) have been developed. Fucostatin I and II are metabolised by the salvage pathway into GDP-analogues, inhibiting *de novo* fucose synthesis. Through co-crystallisation studies, the Fucostatins were shown to inhibit GMD by binding to an allosteric site. The authors noted that FUT inhibition may also have been possible, but GMD inhibition was more likely as after Fucostatin treatment, GDP-4-keto-6-deoxy-mannose and GDP-fucose, two metabolites produced by GMD were reduced. In contrast, GDP-Man, the metabolite substrate of GMD, was increased. These data indicate that the Fucostatin inhibitors act upon GMD by allosteric inhibition (Allen et al., 2016). More recently, Fucotrim I and II, a pair of metabolic fucosylation inhibitors derived from rhamnose 1-phosphate, have also been developed as inhibitors of GMD. Fucotrim I and II are metabolised into their corresponding GDP-Man derivatives and inhibit the *de novo* synthesis pathway of fucose. As the GDP-analogues of the Fucotrim inhibitors increased in concentration in cells, the levels of the endogenous GDP-Fuc metabolites decreased. This accumulation of inhibitory metabolites was shown to cause competitive inhibition of the GMD enzyme (Fig. 5) (Pijnenborg et al., 2021). The availability of inhibitors targeting different stages in fucose synthesis allows for the analysis of each of these enzymes' relative contributions to the metabolic flux of fucosylation. This level of molecular targeting in sialic acid and fucose metabolism will allow researchers to determine the contribution of each of these enzymes to glycan metabolism. As the dysregulation of sialylation and fucosylation is characteristic of inflammation, these chemical inhibitors may have a role in future glycotherapeutics, as they can ameliorate inflammatory hypersialylation & hyperfucosylation.

6. Glycan transporter proteins

6.1. Nucleotide sugar transport proteins

An important factor regulating the metabolic flux of glycans is the transport of activated nucleotide sugars into the Golgi by NST proteins, with specific transporters acting on their target sugars. This group of transport proteins, encoded by the SLC35 genes, also mediate the transfer of nucleotide monophosphate by-products from the Golgi into the cytosol (McDonald et al., 2016), (Szulc et al., 2020). Understanding the mechanisms by which these transporters regulate the supply of activated nucleotide sugars is critical to understanding the metabolic flux of glycosylation.

6.2. Sialic acid transport

The import of CMP-Neu5Ac into the Golgi is regulated by the CMP-Neu5Ac transporter (CST/ SLC35A1) protein, a transmembrane protein in the Golgi and a member of the SLC35 NST group. SLC35A1 is a critical regulator of sialic acid metabolic flux and has been well-characterised. This NST protein interacts with the Sia moiety of CMP-Neu5Ac during its transport into the Golgi lumen in an antiporter mechanism (Maggioni et al., 2013). Rare genetic disorders occur in patients with mutations in the gene encoding SLC35A1. Two mutations, T156R & E196K in the *Slc35a1* gene, significantly reduce the ability of this transporter to move CMP-Neu5Ac into the Golgi, leading to hypsialylation in these patients. When primary fibroblasts from a patient with this rare glycosylation disorder were cultured, transport assays showed that CMP-Neu5Ac transport rates and the final amount of sialylated glycans were reduced significantly (Ng et al., 2017). This analysis of the role that SLC35A1 plays in regulating the flux of activated CMP-Neu5Ac and its effect on downstream sialylation was followed up with an analysis of the structure of SLC35A1. Further analysis of the role that SLC35A1 plays in regulating sialylation was carried out in mice

with megakaryocyte and platelet-specific deletion of the *Slc35a1* gene. This loss of SLC35A1 and its control of CMP-Neu5Ac transport resulted in reduced platelet counts (thrombocytopenia) in these *Plt Slc35a1*^{-/-} modified mice, with the platelets also having a much larger volume than those in the wild-type mice. The platelets in these mice were also shown to have reduced sialylation levels. This desialylation resulted in increased platelet clearance by Kupffer cells in the liver, resulting in thrombocytopenia (Ma et al., 2021). This study shows that sialylation is crucial to the maintenance of healthy platelets. As well as this, it shows that the SLC35A1 transporter, by regulating the levels of CMP-Neu5Ac available to the STs in the Golgi, is a critical regulator of sialic acid metabolism and the regulation of sialylation.

6.3. Fucose transport

Work has also been done to characterise the expression of the protein in the GDP-fucose transporter 1 (FUCT1/SLC35C1) in cancer and acute inflammation. To examine these proteins in a cancer context, the investigators analysed their expression, by quantitative real-time PCR, in mouse lymphoid tumour TIB-63 cells compared to mouse brain endothelial cells as controls. The tumour cells expressed high levels of FX and GMD, the GDP-Fuc transporter protein, SLC35C1, and increased levels of the GDP-Fuc metabolite. The expression of these proteins was then analysed in acute inflammation, using rat kidney allografts as a model. Three days post-transplantation, FX, GMD and the SLC35C1 transporter were all increased before their expression was reduced by day 5 (Niittymäki et al., 2006). These results provide evidence that the expression of nucleotide-sugar transport proteins in the synthesis of fucose is altered in pathological settings such as cancer, and that these proteins could regulate the metabolic flux of fucosylation, by controlling the supply of GDP-Fuc. Subsequent analysis of human colorectal cancer (CRC) tissue samples provided similar results. When the expression of the GDP-Fuc transporter protein was analysed by immunohistochemistry in CRC and healthy tissue samples, 84.3% of the CRC samples expressed the protein, which was significantly higher than the 48.1% of healthy samples. When the fucosylation level of these samples was analysed in these tissue samples with the fucose-binding AAL lectin, the expression of GDP-Fuc transporter matched the levels of fucosylation (Villar-Portela et al., 2013). As the SLC35C1 transports GDP-Fuc into the lumen of the Golgi, increased expression of the transporter would lead to an accumulation of the nucleotide sugar metabolite in the Golgi and the stimulation of FUT enzymes active in the Golgi. These studies, therefore, demonstrate the significant contributions that NST proteins make to the metabolic flux of glycans in inflammatory pathologies such as cancer. As glycosylation (in this case, fucosylation) is modulated in inflammation, a supply of nucleotide sugar metabolites is acted upon by the glycosyltransferase enzymes, resulting in a diverse array of glycan structures.

Recent work has revealed the presence of SLC35C1-independent transport of GDP-Fuc, which can distinguish between substrates generated by the *de novo* and salvage pathways of fucose synthesis (Skurska et al., 2022). GDP-Fuc synthesised by the salvage pathway is the only source which flows through this newly identified transport mechanism. This research used a fucose-supplementation model in SLC35C1-KO cells, comparing core fucosylation between these cells and wild-type cells. The basal level of core fucosylation (α -1,6) of *N*-glycans in the wild-type cells was found to be ~75%, with a much lower rate of 8–10% in the SLC35C1-KO cells. However, when these knockout cells were supplemented with 5 mM fucose for 24 h, core fucosylation was recovered to ~60%. This fucose supplementation also led to a substantial increase in the intracellular concentration of the GDP-Fuc metabolite, with *N*-glycan core fucosylation increasing proportionally with GDP-Fuc in the SLC35C1-KO cells. There was also a higher rate of core fucosylation in the knockout cells, suggesting that these cells utilise the salvage pathway preferentially over the *de novo* pathway of fucose synthesis. To examine the contribution of the *de novo* pathway to fucose synthesis, which involves conversion from mannose, wild-type and

SLC35C1 cells were treated with radioactive mannose precursor. In the knockout cells, the mannose precursor was incorporated into glycans at a level of ~6% compared with the wild-type cells (Skurska et al., 2022). These results provide evidence for SLC35C1-independent transport of GDP-Fuc and show that the Golgi apparatus can distinguish between pools of GDP-Fuc derived from different metabolic pathways. Evidence has also emerged that GLUT-1 can act as an L-fucose plasma membrane transporter (Ng et al., 2023). A transporter knockdown assay, with a siRNA library of 140 transporter proteins, was carried out in HCT116 cells, which have naturally low levels of *de novo* fucosylation due to mutations of GMD. In HCT116 cells tested with this siRNA library, GLUT1 knockdown blocked fucosylation, as indicated by fucose-binding, AAL lectin reactivity. Along with siRNA targeting of the transporters, three essential proteins in exogenous fucose synthesis, SLC35C1, FCSK and FPGT, were knocked down as positive controls. GLUT-1 knockdown significantly reduced AAL reactivity, suggesting that GLUT-1 regulates fucose transport.

Further evidence that GLUT-1 transports fucose came from using two inhibitors of GLUT-1, BAY-876 & WZB117. When the HCT116 cells were treated with 20 nM of BAY-786, fucose uptake was reduced by ~50%, with WZB117 showing a similar inhibitory profile. GLUT-1 KO experiments were also carried out, resulting in similar reductions in fucose uptake. These results reveal a novel GLUT-1-mediated route for plasma membrane fucose transport, which can impact the metabolic flux of fucosylation (Ng et al., 2023). There is, therefore, an opportunity for further research into novel transport routes for these critical regulators of glycosylation, the activated nucleotide sugars. An improved understanding of these NSTs' role will allow for more precise data on their regulation of the metabolic flux of glycosylation.

7. Conclusion

Modifying proteins with *N*-glycans is a highly complex, dynamic process with various regulatory routes. As described in this review, the flux through the metabolic pathways that synthesise *N*-glycans is a dynamic, complex process regulated by multiple factors. These include the concentration of activated nucleotide sugars, the activity and concentration of glycosyltransferase enzymes, the competition between these enzymes and their localisation within the Golgi. Studies using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of different pathologies across a range of organs and tissue types have demonstrated that *N*-glycosylation is dysregulated in disease, and this can serve as a glycosignature of inflammation. Sialylation and fucosylation are two glycosylation types altered substantially during inflammation. This inflammatory hypersialylation and hyperfucosylation are associated with the altered activity of key enzymes in the metabolic pathways synthesising these glycans. The development of metabolic inhibitors of glycosylation has allowed researchers to examine the relative contributions each of these enzymes makes to the synthesis of glycans and to probe their role in inflammation. These inhibitors have also shown therapeutic efficacy, as they can ameliorate the inflammatory changes in glycosylation and resolve pathology. Substantial research has gone into profiling inflammatory changes in *N*-glycosylation and the role that specific metabolic pathways play in these changes. Although the chemical modulators of these pathways and their enzymes show great potential, they have largely remained as tools in research and have only begun to make the transition into trials for diseases in humans. Translating the data linking inflammatory metabolism and glycosignatures of disease with glycosylation into human studies will be the next step in this process, followed by the therapeutic modulation of these pathways in human disease.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aert F. Scheper: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Jack Schofield:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Raghvendra Bohara:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Thomas Ritter:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Abhay Pandit:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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